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Advancing the Implementation and Effectiveness of Payments for Environmental Services (PES) in European Forests

Main findings of a scoping seminar

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1. Introduction

The main objective of this Forum, implemented online on 11/06/2024, was to identify realistic needs and pragmatic demands concerning Payments for Environmental Services (PES) for European forests, hearing from the stakeholders and end-users of two Horizon Europe projects combined: Eco2adapt and INTERCEDE projects. This workshop was thus organised jointly by the two projects, the latter broadly investigating Market Based Instruments (MBI) in Europe, the former being more narrowly focused on PES schemes, as a core part of the broader MBI family. Through a participatory approach, we gathered insights and perspectives that will feed the next forum event organised within Eco2adapt, ensuring continuity in addressing the research-practice gaps in PES implementation in Europe, China and beyond.

Thirty-two participants attended the online seminar. The workshop featured a diverse panel of external participants, including twelve women, showcasing commendable gender diversity. These participants hail from various regions across Europe: from Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic), Northern (Denmark), Western (Austria, France, Germany, United Kingdom), and Southern Europe (Portugal, Spain). This geographical diversity ensured a broad spectrum of perspectives and expertise, enriching the workshop's discussions and outcomes. The professional backgrounds of the participants were varied, encompassing private entities, researchers, policymakers, as well as forestry experts and forest landowners. This heterogeneity fostered a comprehensive dialogue that blended academic insights with practical expertise and on-the-ground experiences.

The seminar started with a few short presentations to set a common conceptual framework. Afterwards, the World Café methodology was employed to gather inputs from participants in the respective 'café corners' dedicated to (1) emergence and design, (2) implementation, and (3) evaluation and upscaling phases of PES. It was encouraged to refer to practical examples, including here some emblematic PES cases from outside Europe (e.g. USA, Mexico).

The World Café process spanned 75 minutes, during which participants rotated through the three rounds of discussions. In each round, only the participants moved to a different session, while the moderator and rapporteur remained at their designated sessions. Both summarized the key points and insights from the previous round to the new group, ensuring continuity and coherence in the discussions. This setup allowed for a thorough exchange of ideas and facilitated a deeper understanding of each phase of the PES implementation cycle.

This report briefly presents the workshop discussions, in the light of the underlying PES theory. As a disclaimer, our discussion summary did not include any independent verification by us of reported claims as made by participants, such as about alleged PES actions and their alleged outcomes. In that sense, reported opinions about the success or failure of certain PES initiatives represent those of particular participants, not necessarily a consensus of all the workshop participants, nor those of us as the authors of the report.

2. How do PES work?

PES are tools to incentivise the supply of forest environmental services (FES), complementing other policy instruments, in particular where regulation alone may not be a feasible or appropriate option. PES are *voluntary transactions between service providers* (e.g., forest owners and managers) *and users, conditional on specific natural resource management rules* (Wunder, 2015). PES can be implemented by a public-sector entity or private beneficiaries, such as hydroelectrical companies. We further define as “PES-like” those instruments that apply a broader PES definition with more flexible elements (e.g., disobeying one of the above-listed definitional criteria).

Looking at the three main policy phases we had pre-identified, PES tend to work effectively under the following conditions:

- (1) **Emergence phase:** The required preconditions include clear land-tenure and access right for prospective FES providers, agreement with FES user on the right payment mode and amounts and, where collective-action elements are relevant, the internally coordinated action between service buyer and seller institutions, respectively.

Specifically, the right payment amount should satisfy both the willingness of service users to pay and the willingness of service providers to accept, with the former needing to exceed the latter: this stands an economic precondition for PES feasibility.

As PES *design* features, the spatial targeting of forest owners to whom payments are offered (participation filters) is an essential element to prioritise areas of special societal and environmental importance, contributing also to higher cost-effectiveness where FES provision and its costs are heterogeneously distributed across the landscape. Differentiated payments could constitute another form of assigning spatial priorities, based on the level of service provided and the provider characteristics and costs. Several other design features can be important, such as paying for measured results rather than actions (e.g., changed forest management) to raise effectiveness, or where relevant establishing collective vs. individual schemes.

- (2) **Implementation phase:** This phase requires sufficient administrative, monitoring and enforcement capacity on behalf of scheme implementers, which can either be buyer-led institutions or designated PES intermediaries. Have an effective monitoring system to understand the degree of PES contract compliance -- and establishing a sanctioning system to deal credibly with incompliance -- are particularly important to meet the contract conditionality, which is at the heart of the PES theory of change (Wunder et al. 2020).
- (3) **Evaluation phase:** is important to understand to what extent the PES scheme has succeeded in its objectives. Ex-post impact evaluation with rigorous techniques such as difference in difference and matching methods should be integrated in PES

programs, conducted by an independent actor to identify biophysical, social and economic impacts. For these methods, a baseline on the ecosystem services targeted is needed in intervention and control areas. Socio-economic impact and permanence of the effects are also part of this phase.

In Europe, the primary example of consolidated functioning PES are agri-environmental schemes promoting sustainable farming practices. Forests-related PES for watershed quality or carbon provision have emerged over the last few decades but remain more nested at the regional or national than at the EU level (Winkel et al., 2022). As a result, regulating and cultural services widely tend to remain unpaid, and externalities caused by the business-as-usual management of forests are unaddressed. Although the European Commission has released a guiding document on the Development of Public and Private Payment Schemes for Forest Ecosystem Services (EC, 2023), the realisation of an EU-wide PES system is still lacking: *de facto* implementation of European PES systems remains in its infancy. Several questions remain open on legal competence, and potential sources of funding. In Europe, the private willingness to pay for incremental ES provision may often be limited due to a historical reliance on tax-financed public environmental management. Additionally, solid monitoring with credible metrics, sanctioning of contractual non-compliance and ES impact evaluation (see below) are fields that need to be further investigated (Winkel et al., 2022).

3. Emergence and Design of PES

Moderator: Georg Winkel (WUR). **Rapporteur:** Ibtissem Taghouti (CTFC).

The first session of the workshop focused on the practical opportunities and challenges encountered in the emergence and design of PES and PES-like schemes. Discussions covered how PES originated, who initiated or lobbied for them, and what factors led their emergence. Participants delved into the primary and secondary objectives of these initiatives, examining the specific ES and desired land management practices they targeted. The main challenges faced during the design phase of PES, included how payment vehicles, incentive amounts, and contracts or commitments were defined.

Looking ahead, participants discussed whether Europe has currently enough forest PES options as needed, identifying any existing niches. The discussion also highlighted best-practice PES designs and explored the barriers preventing their widespread application. Finally, the discussion addressed the key enabling conditions for successful PES, such as specific legal frameworks for private initiatives and the existence of regulated and voluntary carbon markets. We structured the main outcomes of the discussion based on the practical examples of PES and PES-like that participants had shared, highlighting both the successes and challenges (highlighted in **bold**) in the design and implementation across different regions and sectors.

3.1. Opportunities and challenges in the EU (case-specific)

3.1.1. Groundwater Conservation in Denmark, an opportunity for collaboration

Private enterprises and landowners collaborated to establish farming measures and payment schemes aimed at groundwater quality conservation. This collaboration resulted in **a win-win situation. Matching up stakeholder interests was key as a design factor.**

3.1.2. Close-to-Nature Forestry in Denmark requires complementing incentives

Funding for close-to-nature forestry has faced difficulties due to a lack of consensus among landowners regarding the forestry objectives. The experience highlights that current financial incentives alone are insufficient. To achieve agreement and effective PES design may require **a wider approach, complementing financial incentives with nudging mechanisms and search for synergies.**

3.1.3. Long-term green earmarked tax in Croatia challenged by political volatility

For over 30 years, Croatia has implemented a PES-like instrument to promote sustainable forest management (SFM). The State collects a **green earmarked tax** from private enterprises, which goes to a Fund, and is then used to compensate forest owners for SFM practices, including close-to-nature forestry and fire risk management. However, there is a **risk due to political volatility** that these funds might be diverted to other activities, posing a challenge to the programme's stability and effectiveness.

3.1.4. Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certification for FES acting as intermediary

The FSC certification audits sustainable forest management practices through criteria, indicators and their verification. FSC helps forest owners and managers to connect with companies interested in improving FES (recent working line), facilitating private-sector support for sustainable forestry management. On the one hand, **labelling provides formal recognition**, on the other hand, FSC has a **key intermediary role** providing institutional support to catalyse monetary interchanges between companies interested in ecosystem services (ES) and forest managers.

3.1.5. North Italy and Austria: challenges of integrating demand into a market

One significant **challenge identified is the difficulty in converting societal and political demand for ES and biodiversity protection into actual market demand**. In many cases, there is a strong social demand for biodiversity, but no existing market for channelling it into a monetary interchange.

In recreational areas across North Italy and Austria, there is a high willingness to pay (WTP) among visitors (tourists) for the enjoyment of attractive natural spaces. However, the actual payments collected often fall short of the expressed WTP. This discrepancy suggests the need for further ingredients than just the presence of demand to crystallise as a payment.

Beyond existing ES demand, **the rationale of PES requires probably a future ES supply threat**, combined with an economic externality and a credible pathway to payments to produce additional value for money.

3.1.6. Denmark: pro and cons of spatial targeting for efficiency

In Denmark there is ongoing debate about how to allocate PES explicitly to the benefit of biodiversity—incl. whether to prioritize specific areas or distribute funds more broadly among all landowners. **Zoning (i.e. spatial targeting) could improve PES efficiency** as it prioritises critical locations for service delivery. Yet, this **may trigger equity-based objections** from those who conceive the payment as a broad distributional mechanism.

3.2. Opportunities and challenges beyond Europe (case-specific)

3.2.1. Lake Tahoe: PES agreement with water utility company

A case study from the Lake Tahoe region (in Western US) highlights the importance of scientific evidence in demonstrating the effects of forest management on forest ES provision. For a PES arrangement to be successful, ES provided must align with the core interests of the company paying for them. Here the water utility company was primarily concerned with water provision and forest fire prevention, and the PES scheme directly supports its operational needs by reducing future costs. **Scientific evidence** demonstrating the ES effects of forest management **may trigger fund-raising** for PES arrangements if aligning with the core interests of the payer (i.e. medium-term savings).

3.2.2. Mexico: voluntary funding from tourism industry

In Mexico, the **tourism industry has voluntarily funded initiatives to protect coral reefs**, with The Nature Conservancy (TNC) acting formally as the "provider" of these ES. This example

underscores the potential for voluntary funding mechanisms to mobilize resources for ecosystem conservation, driven by the tourism sector's interest in maintaining the health and attractiveness of natural assets that result critical to their business.

3.2.3. UK: Private Voluntary Carbon Markets

This example from the UK revealed that private investments in **voluntary carbon markets**, particularly for afforestation projects, apparently do not always effectively complement **state subsidies**. The **interplay between these two funding sources can sometimes lack coherence, undermining overall outcomes**.

In the UK, new codes are emerging to govern carbon markets for forests and peatlands, generating significant interest among landowners. The government plays a crucial role in creating these codes and calculating total carbon sequestration, ensuring a standardized and transparent process. The implementation involves three key steps:

- *Registration*: Projects are registered in public registers to ensure transparency and public accountability.
- *Documentation and preliminary verification*: Landowners document their projects, and preliminary verification is conducted to issue preliminary credits. This step ensures that the initial estimates of carbon sequestration are accurate and based on documented practices.
- *Final evaluation*: Third-party verifiers are involved in conducting a final evaluation, verifying the calculations, and ensuring that the carbon credits reflect actual sequestration.

This approach has seemed to be particularly successful at the national level in Scotland, showcasing a model for effective carbon market operations. However, questions remain about the long-term management of these forests, including practices related to harvesting and the appropriate time frames for measuring and maintaining carbon sequestration. Addressing these questions is important to ensure the carbon market can deliver genuine environmental benefits while balancing economic and ecological considerations.

Strengthening the alignment between private and public investments increases the chances for maximizing the impact. A policy framework that sets the **structured process** of carbon sequestration initiatives and sets **publicly recognised “credits”** increases trustworthiness towards the mechanism. The **duration of commitment in contracts** affects the permanence of the ES improvements.

3.3. General opportunities and challenges

3.3.1. Providing metrics to showcase ES benefits/impacts

A key point emphasized was the importance of **providing clear metrics** from the very beginning to demonstrate ES benefits and impacts. Some ES are complex and indirectly benefit its users (thus beneficiaries being unaware of their actual benefit), and others are dependent on user perceptions (e.g. recreational opportunities, existence values from conservation). Identifying concrete ES beneficiaries and explicitly present them their benefits

is crucial (in quantitative terms, whenever possible) **to justify and facilitate payments for these services**. Yet, user perceptions may also involve alternative assessment, rather than being fully objectively measurable. Metrics serve as a bridge between theoretical benefits and practical, measurable outcomes.

3.3.2. Internal Demand within the Forest Sector

Within the forest sector itself, ES demand for offsetting purposes is emerging. For instance, a furniture company using timber from intensive forestry practices with some negative impacts is seeking PES to compensate for these effects. Yet, **PES should not become a way for companies to bypass their need to reduce their impacts first**. By positioning PES appropriately, companies can ensure that economic incentives align with environmental goals, promoting more sustainable practices. This strategic placement allows businesses to prioritize avoidance and minimization of environmental impacts first, followed by restoration efforts, and finally using PES to offset any remaining impacts. **PES need to be strategically integrated into the corporate mitigation hierarchy** to first minimise the company's global direct impact, while offsetting then only any residual impact.

3.4. Concluding remarks on PES design phase

The various case studies and examples offered on-the-ground insights into **PES emergence and design** for forest ES in Europe. Although certain forest ES may be facing significant societal demand, converting this into a willingness to pay, and into a PES system, will depend on several factors. This includes ES beneficiaries' perception of an imminent threat to ES supply, on for ES buyers credible pathways to achieve meaningful value for money in ES provisional improvements, and the existence of functioning ES transactional frameworks.

Identified **windows of opportunity** for PES emergence included (i) new regulation of businesses (e.g. ESG, offsetting), (ii) emerging payer-provider mutual interests (e.g. Denmark's groundwater PES, Mexican tourism funds), or (iii) new scientifically grounded data identifying future savings (e.g. Lake Tahoe). A structured process of their planning and verification (e.g. voluntary carbon credits, FSC's ES labelling) can provide robustness to the mechanism – and thus easiness for payers to join.

Some **PES-facilitating factors** have also been identified, including (i) the presence of agents able to raise revenues (e.g. tourism operators), acting as brokers between potential payers and ES suppliers (e.g. FSC) and (ii) spatial targeting. Robustness of the ES outputs may relate to the contract duration, coherence among different public and private initiatives in the same jurisdiction, as well as complementing the economic incentive with other relevant policy tools when needed so.

The main **challenges** discussed include (i) the lack of consensus at practical level (e.g., on forestry objectives), (ii) the need for policy mixes and the risk of policy or funding sources incoherence (e.g., in Denmark and in the UK), (iii) political volatility (e.g., Croatia's green earmarked tax), (iv) risk of perceived inequality when doing spatial targeting, (v) provision of clear performance metrics, and (vi) balance the use of offsetting PES with the responsibility of companies to self-reduce their environmental impact first.

4. Implementation of PES

Moderator: Paola Gatto (UNIPD); **Rapporteur:** Giacomo Pagot (UNIPD)

The second World Café session focused on the practical aspects of implementing PES for forest ES. Participants were expected to delve into identifying the opportunities and challenges, specifically addressing the service providers satisfaction, minimizing transaction costs, ensuring conditional PES, including developing robust monitoring systems, establishing compliance and sanctioning mechanisms to maintain PES integrity.

Additionally, the session involved building a vision for the future implementation of PES by considering whether our understanding of the demand for FES is sufficient, and if more economic valuation is needed. Participants examined if all relevant supply-side scenarios for forest ES were clear and well-defined, and whether the outcomes of PES were monitored closely enough in Europe. They also explored if we have adequate methods for calculating the costs of providing ES, and how transaction costs can be further reduced to make PES more feasible and attractive. By addressing these points, the goal was to develop actionable insights and strategies to improve the implementation of PES, ensuring they are effective, efficient, and equitable in promoting forest ES across Europe.

4.1. Current ES markets and transactions

In general, participants have limited experience with the implementation stage, as existing projects are in the very early stage or not yet implemented.

Most examples involve multiple FES, including primary (e.g., climate change mitigation) and secondary ones (e.g., fire risk control, water management, and biodiversity conservation). A few examples focused solely on single FES, primarily dealing with water services. **Support from public funds is crucial**, particularly in the initial phases of projects. Clear governmental regulations and **a legal framework are essential** to ensure that funds collected through PES are used appropriately.

4.2. Supply-side factors

On the supply side, some factors emerged as key enablers to ensure a smooth PES implementation on the supply side.

Working with associations of landowners, rather than individual landowners, is in some cases critical for successful project implementation. Third-party entities, such as intermediaries with technical expertise and/or local knowledge and social capital, often play a key role in brokering FES-related deals.

Monitoring compliance is crucial for building trust among participants. Standardized monitoring procedures, akin to those used by organizations like the forest certification schemes, are important for **transparent communication** about FES provision and funding utilization.

Monitoring systematically the environmental, economic, and social outcomes resulting from the implementation of these instruments ensures the tracking of PES intended goals, such as reducing emissions, promoting sustainable resource use, or conserving biodiversity.

Effective monitoring is crucial for the success of PES, as it provides the evidence needed to evaluate their impact, improve their design, and build trust among stakeholders.

As barrier to PES implementation, practitioners often lack the technical knowledge and tools needed to measure and map ES effectively.

4.3. Demand-side factors

Discussing the demand side of ES, the two following challenges were mentioned.

In some regions/countries there is currently **no clear data on FES**. National and regional ES inventories are needed to map out specific FES and identify where certain services are most valued. Economic evaluations of ES are necessary, **but translating academic research into practical applications remains a challenge** for practitioners.

A major challenge is **mobilising businesses to pay for ES**, whenever they benefit directly from their critical provision. Accurate impact assessments that outline benefits and costs could potentially persuade businesses to invest, especially if they realize the significant benefits compared to low costs (e.g., public water companies paying a small fee per cubic meter of water).

These findings underscore the complexity of implementing market-based approaches for FES, highlighting the need for supportive policies, technical capacity building, and a clearer understanding of both supply and demand dynamics.

4.4. Concluding remarks on implementation phase

In conclusion, our discussions have illuminated both the promise and the challenges inherent in implementing market-based approaches for ES. While most initiatives are in their nascent stages, there is a clear consensus on the pivotal role of public funding and supportive regulatory frameworks in driving successes. The diversity of the ES addressed, from climate change mitigation to water management and biodiversity conservation, underscores multifaceted societal demands and the interconnected nature of environmental benefits.

As key **opportunities and enablers**, collaborative efforts with associations of landowners and intermediaries equipped with technical expertise emerged as key facilitators for project implementation. However, ensuring transparency through rigorous monitoring and bridging the technical knowledge gap among practitioners is crucial for building trust and maximizing the impact of FES projects.

As **challenges**, particularly on the demand side, efforts to identify and stimulate ES demand must be prioritized, creating long-term data inventories. Additionally, businesses need to be persuaded to invest through clear communication of benefits. These insights underscore the need for continued collaboration, innovation, and strategic investment to unlock the full potential of PES in preserving and enhancing our natural ecosystems.

5. Evaluation and upscaling of PES

Moderator: Thomas Lundhede (UCPH); **Rapporteur:** Josep Ollé (CTFC)

Participants in the third session explored opportunities and challenges surrounding the evaluation and upscaling of PES. Discussions focused on assessing the perceived successes and shortcomings of PES in achieving their primary and secondary objectives, emphasizing whether ex-ante baselines had been established for informing PES outcomes.

The session scrutinized the necessity for rigorous quantitative impact evaluations alongside qualitative evidence, exploring issues such as participant motivation, potential monetary crowding-out effects on intrinsic motivations, the durability of PES-triggered benefits, plus threats to efficiency such as leakage. Cost-effectiveness of PES was perceived as a central yet under-researched theme, including for evaluating the feasibility of scaling PES vertically and horizontally. Visionary discussions aimed to define realistic aspirations for future PES, including to identify essential information needs such as databases for establishing the baselines needed for comprehensive impact evaluations. Participants collectively identified barriers preventing more rigorous impact assessments. They also considered the potential scale-up of various types of PES, including in the light of which ES necessitated landscape-scale or cross-boundary approaches. The session also explored the integration of PES within more intricate policy mixes to optimize their effectiveness in achieving environmental and socio-economic goals.

5.1. Permanence

Unclear functioning of voluntary markets discourages funding, as exemplified in recent years by carbon markets. Carbon farming regulation could shed some light, but still a set of better regulated carbon markets may arguably be needed eventually. A policy framework is needed to engage payers and ensure the permanence of ES.

As challenge to permanence, discontinuous demand hinders the emergence and contribution of a PES system. In the Czech Republic, an NGO purchased land for conservation and planned to fund it through donations, but faced financial difficulties due to decreased demand. Similarly, WWF Bulgaria collaborated with a cosmetic company to sponsor a forest by paying the owner not to cut trees, but the initiative ended after three years when the funding ceased.

Ensuring long-term economic contributions is important for FES, as forest management requires continuity over several years.

5.2. Socioeconomic impact

Participants observed a **significant lack of knowledge** and information about PES, especially among small landowners. For example, in the Czech Republic, forest owners are generally open to PES schemes but need a clearer understanding of the benefits and mechanisms involved, and to grasp adequately how payments were defined. In Croatia, it has been seen that landowners often do not understand the rationale behind the public objectives for FES provision. To achieve these targets, compensation payments are necessary to adopt practices they might initially not understand, nor see as desirable. **The engagement of private forest owners is thus key to ensure a positive impact at the socioeconomic level, too.**

5.3. Environmental impact

In Denmark, companies sometimes buy land for afforestation projects to gain credits, but the subsequent land use might not necessarily align with the best ecosystem use. A **public-private collaboration would be desirable**, so the public could decide which is the most preferred ecosystem use.

New methodologies and standards for carbon footprint in afforestation and reforestation projects are being developed in the UK, involving ex-ante carbon calculations of a 20% reserve buffer of the projected credits. Public evaluators check in the field the actual forest growth and eventually unlock the rest of the payment. A **solid baseline scenario is needed** to measure and contrast the progress achieved as a result of the payment.

PES system accuracy and credibility can sometimes result in expensive planning and monitoring costs. Yet, financial feasibility is crucial as well. Hence, **a compromise needs to be struck between robustness and simplicity**.

5.4. Concluding remarks from the evaluation & upscaling phase

Sound impact evaluation, and eventual upscaling towards streamlined PES models, exhibited a critical need for enhanced knowledge, understanding the parameters that likely drive PES effectiveness. Establishing clear ex-ante baselines and conducting thorough ex-post evaluations are essential for accurately assessing PES outcomes. Furthermore, these outcomes will often be heterogeneous over time and space with respect to different contexts, design and implementation modalities.

Overcoming the traditional dichotomy in monitoring practices—i.e., balancing rigorous quantitative metrics with qualitative insights—is crucial for such a comprehensive understanding of PES impacts. Robust policy support and guidance can play a pivotal role in steering PES initiatives toward success, including to make sure that the existing legislation is supporting PES. Sharing best practices and successful case studies is vital for scaling up PES vertically (e.g., from pilots to the national level), as well as horizontally ‘scaling out’ PES across similarly sized watersheds or regions. By fostering a collaborative environment where insightful experiences and good practices are widely disseminated, we may enhance the adoption and efficacy of PES, thus ultimately also achieving broader environmental and socio-economic benefits.

6. Conclusions and perspectives

This report examines the potentials and challenges of implementing Payments for Environmental Services (PES) in European forest settings, as they emerged from participant discourses during our workshop. We highlight the promise of PES to drive environmental objectives in a targeted manner, while we are also identifying significant design and operational complexities: while the basic set-up behind PES sounds simple, the devil is in the details with respect to meeting the requirements both for setting up a PES scheme, and to run it in a way that delivers the hoped-for results.

Among our key recommendations, we emphasize the importance of developing robust PES frameworks that integrate insights from both theory and stylized practice from PES implementation across the world. Ensuring sustained public funding for essentially public-nature ES (such as those derived from well-conserved biodiversity) and supportive regulation will be crucial in fostering the growth of PES initiatives. Furthermore, engaging businesses through clear communication of the benefits associated with PES can stimulate demand and encourage investment, thus playing a strategically complementary role – and in some cases, providing the seed funding for new modalities that the public sector is not yet engaged in (e.g., the recent expansion in biodiversity credit pilots).

Collaborative efforts of ES buyers or users with landowners, sometimes through intermediaries, are essential for building trust and facilitating successful project implementation. Fostering robust monitoring and knowledge-sharing can thus further enhance PES effectiveness and replicability.

7. Next Steps within the Eco2adapt project

The next steps involve a multifaceted approach to engagement and communication. First, we will engage in a series of policy-relevant events in Europe to gather more insights on the status of PES initiatives in Europe. Secondly, we will organise a forum, as an online or hybrid meeting to engage both the European and Chinese stakeholders, and bring comparative reflections to the discussion. We foresee further collaboration with the INTERCEDE project, as well active participation to their events to further study PES in Europe.

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